

OX²⁰²²GVC

Oxford Geoheritage Virtual Conference

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ABSTRACT VOLUME**

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Keynote Abstracts, followed by Abstract Volume

All times given in British Summer Time (UTC+1)

PHOTOGRAMMETRIC 3D MODELS OF THE CLIFFS OF LUMIGNANO GEOSITE (N. ITALY) FOR GEOHERITAGE DOCUMENTATION AND GEOCONSERVATION.

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Presentation Format: *Flash Talk (5 minutes, maximum of 3 slides)*

Presentation Day: **Wednesday**

Presentation Time: **4:35:00 PM**

Presentation Number/Poster Group: **18**

ABSTRACT:

In the last few years, the theme of the geoheritage has gained more and more importance. The cliffs of Lumignano, a little village located in Veneto region (Italy), are an example of complex and unique geology, important for both science and tourism. The geology of Lumignano tells the history of an early Oligocene (ca. 33 Ma) coral reef which was set up at a global sea-level drop, due to the Antarctic ice cap emplacement, and which was then cut by volcanic conduits and faults. Those episodes generated spectacular limestone walls, dotted by hundreds of caves, and renown as a climbing area. This work, which is part of the GeoKart project (Interreg Italy-Slovenia), aims to visualize the geodiversity and geoheritage of Lumignano. In order to do that, we produced 3D models of 3 rock walls and 2 quarries, considered the best geoheritage sites of the area, through photogrammetry. These rock walls are on average 300 m wide and 50 m high. We acquired an average of 150÷350 pictures per site using a Dji Phantom 4 RTK. Pictures were georeferenced with an error in the order of centimeters directly during the survey. Then, we used Agisoft Metashape to generate point clouds, which were cleaned of inaccurate data. Meshes were then generated and texturized with the pictures. We finally obtained 5 models of the areas of study with an average spatial resolution of 5 cm and an average vertical accuracy of 4.5 cm. Those models represent important documentation of the geoheritage of Lumignano which, especially in the quarries, is potentially subjected to degradation. Moreover, those models have been decimated and uploaded on sketchfab (<https://sketchfab.com>). Using a QR code, models can be accessed by the broader public of tourists, educators, and local administrators. We also used Virtual Reality Geoscience and Lime software to draw geological features, e.g., facies boundaries and fault planes. In Sketchfab, interactive buttons were positioned directly on the points of interest of the model. Those buttons link to explanations of specific geological features on the rock wall.